

METHODOLOGY FOR APPLYING INTERACTIVE LEARNING IN THE EDUCATIONAL SPACE OF SCHOOL, PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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Annotation. The article introduces the methodology of interactive learning; the issues of equipping schools with interactive learning tools are considered.

Key words: interactive methods, interactive tools, problems and prospects of interactive learning.

The concept of interactive learning appeared relatively recently - in the 1990s. And this is still far from the most developed area of pedagogy. Thus, theorists have not yet come to a consensus on whether interactive teaching methods should be classified as a separate category. In addition, it is not uncommon for only learning using interactive digital technologies to be considered interactive.

This article is about what interactive learning is and how it differs from other types, what principles it is based on and what teaching methods can be called interactive.

Interactive learning is called learning that involves constant interaction between the teacher and students, students with each other, or students with the educational environment. In interactive learning, there is a mutual exchange of information, and the actions of different participants in the educational process influence each other.

And here a difficulty arises. Thus, the division of teaching methods into active and passive is widespread. In passive learning, the main role belongs to the teacher - he acts as a source of knowledge that students must learn. A typical example of a passive teaching method is a lecture: the teacher explains the topic, and students take notes on this material to later repeat it in the exam.

Active learning implies that the student is no longer an object to whom the teacher transfers knowledge, but an independent subject. He constructs his knowledge by searching and analyzing information, conducting experiments, and so on. An example of an active learning method is a project activity in which the student investigates a problem or problem and creates a product to solve it.

Interactive methods are based on the exchange of information when the teacher creates conditions and guides students. Interactive teaching methods look much more complicated than others, because the teacher is not the main participant in the pedagogical process. But the result usually lives up to expectations.

Если посмотреть на принципы интерактивных методов, то можно увидеть, что они включают в себя как равенство всех участников, так и отсутствие критики личности. При применении на уроках интерактивного обучения учащиеся во время урока ведут себя более деятельно и восприимчивы к материалу, чем при других методиках, об этом пишут авторы [7,8,9,10].

Использование интерактивных методов обучения в школе не всегда проходит без трудностей. Во-первых, это отсутствие интерактивных средств обучения, таких как интерактивные доски, планшеты, проекторы, плазменные панели и пр. Во-вторых, это нежелание педагогов применять новейшие методы интерактивного обучения на уроках. Трудности в применении интерактивных методов возникают из-за незнания учителя содержания метода и отсутствия практики его применения в школе. В связи с этим встает острая необходимость в организации курсов повышения квалификации по разъяснению содержания и применения интерактивного обучения в образовательном пространстве школы.

Volgina N.A., Abramov I.G., Verbitsky A.A., Borisova N.V. made a significant contribution to the study of interactive teaching methods. K. Levine argues that most

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effective changes in people's attitudes and behavior are easier to implement in a group rather than in an individual context [6].

T. Panina says that “interactive learning presupposes a different logic of the educational process from the usual one: not from theory to practice, but from the formation of new experience to its theoretical understanding through application” [6].

The main problem of using interactive teaching methods in a modern school was and is the understanding of the role and use of information technology by teachers.

In 2019, 4 schools in the city of Termez received multifunctional complexes. With the help of federal subsidies, interactive whiteboards, tablets, computers, webcams, etc. appeared in school classrooms. A lesson conducted using interactive methods is always interesting, because every student is involved in the educational process. Depending on the specific lesson, one group of students can study with tablets, another group can work with an interactive whiteboard, and a third group can work with a webcam.

And it is not unimportant that the teacher manages the entire educational process from his computer. When conducting an experimental study on the use of interactive teaching methods with 7th grade students, at the beginning of the quarter, topics were distributed to prepare for specific lessons using a specific interactive method. This approach gives time to better prepare for a reporting lesson or role-playing game. Students, already prepared with the material, speak in front of the class and thereby involve their classmates in the game. IN

School No. 9 in Termez, during history lessons, teachers actively use interactive teaching methods using a multifunctional complex. The most common methods include lesson report, role-playing game and clusters.

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